

(Table 1 contd.)

N-Isonicotinoyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)azopyrazoles (3)				
H	240	40	Light brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S
Guanido	245	60	Yellow oohor	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃ S
2,6-Dimethylpyrimidinyl	250	55	Dirty green	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₃ S
2,4-Dimethylpyrimidinyl	240	56	Dirty brown	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₃ S
Pyrimidinyl	215	60	Dirty brown	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S
Acetyl	260d	55	Dirty brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S
Phenylazoyl	240	50	Dust colour	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₃ S
Methiazoyl	230d	55		C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S
Thiazoyl	160	50	Yellow colour	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S
Methoxy-pyrazinoyl	225	65	Greyish black	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S
Methoxazoyl	250	60	Light brown	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₃ S

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

to cool overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as light brown crystals (3; 60%), m.p. 215° (Found: N, 24.00. C₂₁H₁₈N₆O₃S calcd. for: N, 24.19%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 150 (NH), 1 150–1 320 (SO₂), 1 530–1 580 (N=N), 1 660 (CO), 2 950–2 960 (CH₃) and 760 cm⁻¹ (Ph); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.50 (6H, 2CH₃), 7.85 (H, NH) and 8.0–8.40 (Ar).

The other derivatives (3) were prepared in the same way by varying the substituent (Table 1), viz., R=guanido; 2,4-dimethylpyrimidinyl; 2,6-dimethylpyrimidinyl; acetyl; pyrimidinyl; phenazoyl; methiazoyl; thiazoyl; methoxy pyrazinoyl; and methoxazoyl; and their characteristics are given in Table 1.

N-Isonicotinoyl-3-methyl-6-aminophenyl-4-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)azopyrazole (3a): To a solution of 2-(4'-sulphamoylphenyl)hydrazono-1-aminobutane-1,3-dione (2; 0.002 mol) in acetic acid (20.0 ml), a solution of isonicotinoylhydrazine (0.002 mol) in acetic acid was added and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol as brown crystals (3a; 55%), m.p. 235° (Found: N, 23.42. C₂₄H₁₉N₇O₃S calcd. for: N, 20.20%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 145 (NH), 1 160–1 320 (SO₂), 1 530–1 570 (N=N), 1 665 (CO), 2 950–2 960 (CH₃) and 760 cm⁻¹ (Ph).

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Synthesis of s-Triazine Derivatives

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S-Triazines^{1,2} and urea and thiourea derivatives^{3,4} possess wide range of biological activity. With a view to study their antibacterial activity, N¹-(2,4-dianilino-s-triazine-6-yl-aminoacetyl)-N²-arylureas (2) and N¹-(2-aryl-amino-4- α,β -dicarboxyethylamino-s-triazine-6-yl)-N²-o-nitrophenylthioureas (4) were synthesised. Reaction of N-(2,4-dianiline-s-triazine-6-yl)-aminoacetyl chloride (1) with N-arylureas gave 2, and 4 were obtained by the reaction of 3 with o-nitrophenylthiourea. The antibacterial activity of 2 and 4 has been studied by cup-plate method at a concentration of 3 mg ml⁻¹.

Experimental

General method of preparation of N^1 -(2,4-dianilino-*s*-triazine-6-yl-aminoacetyl)- N^2 -arylureas (2): A solution of N^1 -(2,4-dianilino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)aminoacetyl chloride^{5,6} (0.01 mol) and arylurea (0.02 mol) in dioxane or acetone was refluxed for 3 h on a steam-bath. The gummy mass obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice was dissolved in acetone and diluted with ice-cold water to yield a solid. The solid was treated with aqueous 2% NaOH and boiled with water to remove the acid impurities and arylurea, respectively, and crystallised from dioxane.

N -(2-Chloro-4-arylamino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)-aspartic acid (3): A solution of L-aspartic acid (0.01 mol) in acetone was added to a solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) in acetone and stirred at 0–5° for 2 h. To the resulting solution containing N -(2,4-dichloro-*s*-triazine-6-yl)aspartic acid, a solution of aromatic amine (0.01 mol) in acetone was added and stirred at 35–45° for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised to give 3.

N^1 -(2-Arylamino-4- α,β -dicarboxyethylamino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)- N^2 -*o*-nitrophenylthioureas (4): An equimolar mixture of *o*-nitrophenylthiourea (prepared from *o*-nitroaniline, benzyl chloride and ammonium thiocyanate) and 3 was refluxed in acetone at 80–90° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from DMF to yield 4; $\nu_{\max}$ 870–770 (C_3N_3), 1 740–1 680 (NHCONH), 1 520–1 480 (NHCSNH), 1 700–1 680 (COOH) and 1 430–1 400 cm^{-1} (CH_2COOH).

Physical data of compounds 2 and 4 are given in Table 1. M.ps. are uncorrected. The ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Backmann IR-5 spectrophotometer.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 4*

Sl. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ (1=1)
Compound 2				
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	225	75	—
2.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	185	71	—
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	190	73	—
4.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	200	68	—
5.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	170	70	—
6.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	214	76	—
7.	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	210	69	—
8.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	185	74	—
Compound 4				
9.	C ₆ H ₅	275	70	+59.0
10.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	290	73	+61.0
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	350	65	+69.0
12.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	167	78	+56.0
13.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	217	61	+71.0
14.	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	206	76	+62.0
15.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	192	70	+53.0
16.	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ COO ₂ H ₄	198	69	+51.0

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Biological activity: The compounds were screened against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by using their ethanol solution.

The maximum zone of inhibition was observed against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in 2 (3.5 and 2.0 mm, respectively). The nitro derivatives were more active than others. The thioureas (4) having *o*-anisyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-chlorophenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl groups in the *s*-triazine ring were most active against *E. coli*; while against *S. aureus*, the *para*-substituted products exhibited higher activity than the *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds.

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Variation of Major Constituents of Essential Oil of the Leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn.

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OCIMUM sanctum Linn. (Family : Labiatae), a sacred basil, is an indigenous (doubtfully) aromatic annual plant well known for its essential oil, and its constituents have wide range pharmaceutical and perfumery uses¹. Available literature indicates^{2–5} that there is a great deal of variation in the composition of essential oil of *O. sanctum* grown in different localities. It has been reported^{6,7} that the reproductive stage of the plant exerts considerable influence on the quantity and quality of the oil. But no detailed chemical investigation has yet been done on the variation of essential oil constituents during the yearly reproductive developmental stages.

The present paper deals with the variation of the amount and the major constituents of the essential oil of the leaves at various stages of growth throughout a year.